

A Non-ionic Seed Gum from *Cassia sophera*

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A water soluble polysaccharide has been extracted from *Cassia sophera* seeds with cold acidulated water and purified to give polysaccharide containing D-galactose and D-mannose in 1 : 3 molar ratio. Acid catalysed fragmentation, periodate oxidation, methylation and enzymic hydrolysis showed that the seed-gum has a branched structure consisting of linear chain of β -D-(1 \rightarrow 4) linked mannopyranosyl units, some of which are substituted at O-6 by one α -D-(1 \rightarrow 6) galactopyranosyl units. Methylation analysis of the galactomannan furnished 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose, 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose, 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose in the molar ratio 1 : 1 : 2. Both the methylation and the periodate-oxidation studies showed 25% of end-groups. The significance of these results, together with the findings of partial hydrolysis with acid, are discussed in relation to ascertaining the structure of the polysaccharide.

THE plant *Cassia sophera* (N.O. Leguminosae) is reported to be highly medicinal¹. Due to the high medicinal value and increasing industrial acceptance of the plant mucilages, the seed mucilage from this plant has now been subjected to extensive structural study.

Experimental

Paper chromatography was conducted at room temperature by the descending technique using the following solvent mixtures (v/v): (A) 1-butanol-ethanol-water² (5 : 1 : 4), (B) butan-1-ol-propan-2-ol-water³ (11 : 6 : 3), (C) ethyl acetate-pyridine-water⁴ (10 : 4 : 3) and (D) ethyl acetate-pyridine-water⁵ (2 : 1 : 2), and detection with aniline hydrogen phthalate. All evaporations were conducted under diminished pressure at 35–40°. Melting points are uncorrected, and all specific rotations were measured at equilibrium. Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺) ion-exchange resin was used for decationising the hydrolysates, and all residues were dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. The enzyme emulsin used was extracted from almonds.

Isolation of the polysaccharide: Crushed seeds (1 kg) were successively extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 60–80°) and ethanol and then stirred with 1.5% acetic acid for 24 h at room temperature. The acid extract was slowly added with stirring to ethanol (5 vol) to give a crude product. Dissolution and reprecipitation were repeated and the polysaccharide was collected, washed with ethanol and dried.

Purification of the polysaccharide: The dried polysaccharide was redissolved in water and the solution was shaken well with chloroform and then centrifuged, whereupon the denatured proteins formed at the water-chloroform interface⁶, a gel, was removed. This treatment was repeated 5 times to remove all the proteins. An excess of Fehling's

solution was added to the deproteinised aqueous solution of the polysaccharide, and a copper complex was precipitated⁷. The complex was centrifuged, washed thoroughly with dilute Fehling's solution and suspended in cold water. The complex was decomposed with 1N hydrochloric acid. The polysaccharide was regenerated by slowly adding the solution to ethanol (5 vol) with stirring; the pure product was reprecipitated from its solution in 1% acetic acid by ethanol to yield non-reducing white amorphous material, ash content 0.1%, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 70^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in water).

Homogeneity of the polysaccharide: The polysaccharide (1.5 g) was fractionally precipitated⁸ from aqueous solution (300 ml) by the addition of ethanol (400 and 800 ml). Two fractions, (a) and (b), were collected by centrifugation, washed with ethanol and dried. Hydrolysis of fractions (a) and (b) gave D-galactose and D-mannose in the molar ratios of 1 : 3, and both fractions retained the original specific rotation $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 70^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in water).

The polysaccharide (1 g) was treated with acetic anhydride-sodium acetate⁹ and the resulting acetate (600 mg) had $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 36$ (c, 0.2 in chloroform); deacetylation regenerated material having $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 70.5^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in water).

The polysaccharide (50 mg) was subjected to conventional zone-electrophoresis^{9,10} on Whatman no. 1 paper in 0.05M sodium tetraborate (pH 9.2) for 9 h at 320 V and 3.7 mA. A plot of the absorbance against segment number showed only a single sharp peak.

Investigation of the polysaccharide:

Hydrolysis: The purified polysaccharide (1 g) was hydrolysed with 1 M sulphuric acid for 36 h at 100°. Pc (solvent C) of the hydrolysate revealed D-galactose (R_f 0.15) and D-mannose (R_f 0.21). Identities were confirmed by co-chromatography

with authentic samples and preparation of derivatives, and the absolute configuration from the specific rotation, D-galactose, m.p. 164°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 80^\circ$ (c, 0.6 in water); D-galactose phenylhydrazone, m.p. 153°; D-mannose, m.p. 131°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 14^\circ$ (c, 0.2 in water); D-mannose phenylhydrazone, m.p. 198°.

The polysaccharide (300 mg) together with D-ribose (30 mg) as a reference sugar was treated with 1M sulphuric acid for 36 h at 100°. A portion (1 ml) of the hydrolysate was subjected to pc (solvent B) on Whatman no. 3 paper and the individual monosaccharides were quantified⁸ by periodate oxidation. Assuming 100% recovery of ribose, the molar ratio of galactose to mannose was 1 : 3.

Graded hydrolysis¹¹: The polysaccharide (300 mg) was hydrolysed with 25 mM sulphuric acid (40 ml) for 4 h at 100°. The hydrolysate was subjected to pc (solvent B) after 5, 15, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180, 210 and 240 min, and galactose was found to be liberated first followed by mannose.

Periodate oxidation: To a solution of the polysaccharide (300 mg, 30 ml) were added KCl (2.5 g) and sodium metaperiodate (0.25 M, 25 ml). The volume was made to 100 ml with water and the mixture stored in dark at room temperature. Aliquots (2 ml) were withdrawn at intervals, and after the excess of periodate had been reduced with ethylene glycol, titrated with 0.01 M sodium hydroxide, the formic acid liberated was 0.154 mmol per 100 g. After 84 h, an excess (30 ml) of ethylene glycol was added, the solution evaporated and the residue hydrolysed. Pc (solvent B) of the hydrolysate then revealed only mannose. To a solution of the polysaccharide (300 mg in 30 ml water) was added sodium metaperiodate (0.25 M, 30 ml) and the volume made up to 100 ml with water. The uptake of periodate was determined¹² at intervals. The uptake became constant in 96 h and corresponding to 0.84 mol per 100 g of the polysaccharide. After 96 h, the oxopolysaccharide was hydrolysed as already described; neither galactose nor mannose was detected.

Methylation: The polysaccharide (6 g) was methylated by Hakomori method¹³ followed by two Purdie's methylations¹⁴. The completely methylated polysaccharide had $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 45^\circ$ (c, 0.2 in chloroform). The methylated derivative (1.5 g) was hydrolysed with 90% formic acid for 6 h at 100° and then with 0.75 M sulphuric acid for 10 h at 100°, and the products were fractionated on Whatman no. 3 paper (solvent A), with 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose (TMG) as the reference, to give the following products: (i) 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-D-galactose, RTMG 0.87, m.p. 72–73°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 120^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in water) (lit.¹⁵ m.p. 74°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 121^\circ$); the anilide, m.p. 192–193°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 43^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in acetone) (lit.¹⁵ m.p. 194°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 45^\circ$); (ii) 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose-syrup, RTMG 0.53, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 16^\circ$ (c, 0.9 in water) (lit.¹⁶ -15.8°); the anilide, m.p. 136° (lit.¹⁵ 138°); (iii) 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose, RTMG 0.81, syrup $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 11^\circ$ (c, 1.2 in water) (lit.¹⁷ -10°); the derived phenylhydrazide, m.p. 121–131° (lit.¹⁸ 137°).

The methylated polysaccharide (300 mg) together with added D-glucose as a reference, was treated with 0.75 M sulphuric acid for 16 h at 100°. The resulting methylated sugars were separated by pc (solvent A), and quantified by titration with alkaline hypiodite. The molar ratio of fractions 1 to 3 were 1 : 1 : 2.

Partial hydrolysis: The polysaccharide (4 g) was hydrolysed with 0.05 M sulphuric acid for 14 h at 100°. The hydrolysate was subjected to preparative pc (solvent D), and elution of the fractions with distilled water gave D-galactose, D-mannose and the following oligosaccharides: (i) epimelbiose, α -D-Galp(1→6)-D-Manp¹⁹, m.p. 199°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 120^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in water) (lit.¹⁹ m.p. 201–202°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 123 - 24^\circ$; acid hydrolysis gave galactose and mannose and methylation followed by hydrolysis gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose; (ii) mannobiose, β -D-Manp(1→4)-D-Manp^{20,21}, m.p. 203–05° (from ethanol), $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 9^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in water) (lit.²⁰ m.p. 202–03°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 5.2$ to -8.2°); the derived phenyllosazone, m.p. 204° (lit.¹⁹ 203–06°); acid hydrolysis gave mannose only (pc) and emulsin hydrolysed the disaccharide indicating a β -linkage; methylation followed by hydrolysis gave 2,3,4,6-tetra- and 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose; (iii) mannotriose, β -D-Manp(1→4)- β -D-Manp(1→4)-D-Manp^{20,21}, m.p. 135–62°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 13^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in water) (lit.²¹ m.p. 134–65°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 15$ to -26°); acid hydrolysis gave (pc) mannose only and partial hydrolysis with 1N sulphuric acid gave mannobiose and mannose; methylation followed by hydrolysis gave 2,3,4,6-tetra- and 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose. The trisaccharide was cleaved by emulsin showing the presence of β -linkages.

Results and Discussion

The polysaccharide was extracted from the defatted seeds of *Cassia sophera* with 1% acetic acid and by repeated precipitation from its solution therein with ethanol. It was purified by repeated deproteinisation using chloroform and by complexation with Fehling's solution. The homogeneity of the polysaccharide was verified by fractional precipitation, zone-electrophoresis and *via* acetylation and deacetylation. The white amorphous polysaccharide was water soluble and had $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 70^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in water), 1% ash content, and a negligible percentage of methoxyl, acetyl groups and uronic acid. Complete hydrolysis of the polysaccharide yielded galactose and mannose in the molar ratio 1 : 3. Graded acid hydrolysis with 25 mM sulphuric acid resulted in the favoured removal of galactose, suggesting the presence of α -linked D-galactose units on the periphery, as end-groups.

To determine the position of linkage between the monosaccharide units of the galactomannan, it was exhaustively methylated, first by the Hakomori method and then by Purdie's method to afford a brown semi-solid glassy mass that had $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 46^\circ$

